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СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫЙ НОМЕР 1

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SANITARY AND HYGIENIC MONITORING OF PESTICIDE POLLUTION OF FOOD PRODUCTS IN UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

Food products are the main source of possible entry into the human body of chemical compounds - pesticides used in the cultivation of crop and livestock products. The large-scale sanitary and hygienic monitoring carried out in the republic (2017-2021) of pesticide residues in food products based on high-precision analytical methods makes it possible to identify the range of pesticides present and the degree of damage to products relative to the hygienic regulations.

Keywords: pesticides, pollution, food products, monitoring, analytical control.

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САНИТАРНО-ГИГИЕНИЧЕСКИЙ МОНИТОРИНГ ЗАГРЯЗНЕННОСТИ ОСТАТОЧНЫМИ КОЛИЧЕСТВАМИ ПЕСТИЦИДОВ ПИЩЕВЫХ ПРОДУКТОВ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Пищевые продукты являются основным источником возможного поступления в организм человека химических соединений – пестицидов, применяемых при выращивании продуктов растениеводства и животноводства. Проводимый в республике годах широкомасштабный санитарно-гигиенический мониторинг (2017-2021 г.г.) остаточных количеств пестицидов в продуктах питания на основе высокоточных аналитических методов позволяет выявлять ассортимент присутствующих ядохимикатов и степень пораженности продуктов относительно гигиенического регламента.

Ключевые слова: пестициды, загрязнение, пищевые продукты, мониторинг, аналитический контроль.

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O‘ZBEKISTONDA OZIQ-OVQAT PESTITSIDLARINING QOLDIQ MIQDORI BILAN IFLOSLANISHINING SANITARIYA-GIGIYENA MONITORINGI

ANNOTATSIYA

Oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari kimyoviy birikmalar - o'simlik va chorvachilik mahsulotlarini etishtirishda ishlatiladigan pestitsidlarning inson tanasiga kirishining asosiy manbai hisoblanadi. Respublikada (2017-2021 yillar) oziq-ovqat mahsulotlaridagi pestitsidlar qoldiqlarining yuqori aniqlikdagi tahliliy usullarga asoslangan keng ko‘lamli sanitariya-gigiyena monitoringi mavjud bo‘lgan pestitsidlar assortimentini va mahsulotlarning zararlanish darajasini aniqlash imkonini beradi. mamlakatning turli mintaqalarida gigiyena qoidalari.

Kalit so'zlar: pestitsidlar, ifloslanish, oziq-ovqat, monitoring, analitik nazorat

Introduction. The Strategy for the Development of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030 [8] is aimed at implementing reforms in the agro-food sector, ensuring food security and increasing the competitiveness of food products in the world market. One of the priority tasks set is to ensure the safety and quality of food products in accordance with international standards, which would allow Uzbekistan to join the World Trade Organization. To date, the country is actively introducing the Concept for the development of production of organic agricultural and organic food products [7]. Previously, in the production of agricultural and food products, pesticides with high toxicity and resistance were intensively used. In the world over the past decades, a significant amount of hazardous and difficult to decompose pesticides in the environment has been withdrawn from circulation and use. Currently, preference is given to low-toxic chemicals that quickly decompose in the soil and positively affect the yield [3].

However, as scientific studies show, their residual amounts still have a negative impact on the soil and crops cultivated on it, natural water sources, fish farming and animal husbandry, and, as one participant in the food chain, human health [4].

In the world, the modern range of pesticides is represented by hundreds of thousands of preparations. It has been shown that the composition of preparations approved in Uzbekistan for use as plant protection products includes about 60 ingredients recognized as “highly hazardous pesticides (HHPs) at the international level and 34 of them are prohibited in other countries” [2]. In this regard, sanitary and hygienic monitoring of contamination with residual amounts of pesticides in environmental objects, food products and their control based on sensitive research methods becomes timely and relevant.

The purpose of the study was to conduct sanitary and hygienic monitoring to differentiate and identify the degree of contamination of food products with residual quantities of pesticides in the whole country and in the context of regions.

Material and research methods. The results of large-scale monitoring studies in the whole country in the period from 2017 to 2021 are analyzed. Residual quantities of pesticides were detected in crop and livestock products. The amount of residues of pesticides determined was carried out by highly informative analytical methods: high-performance liquid and gas chromatography, thin-layer chromatography, chromato-mass spectrometry. Methods for the determination of all studied pesticides are metrologically certified and included in the “State Register of Methods for Quantitative Chemical Analysis and Assessment of the Condition of Environmental Objects”, approved for state sanitary and hygienic control and monitoring.

Results and its discussion.

Today, there are various methodological approaches to determine pesticide residues in a variety of foods. The reliability and accuracy of our results were ensured by a combination of high performance liquid and gas chromatography, thin layer chromatography and mass spectrometry. The complexity of the analysis of determining the residual amounts of pesticides is due to the identification of a negligible content of pesticides, the presence of several types of pesticides in the sample, the presence of impurities that interfere with the identification of the pesticide, etc. The analysis of the data obtained during the monitoring showed that the contamination of food raw materials and food products with residual amounts of pesticides in the study period in the republic as a whole is represented by organochlorine pesticides, organophosphorus pesticides, synthetic and others (Fig. 1).

It was revealed that the share of residual quantities of organochlorine pesticides (OCP) in food products produced in the republic significantly prevails among the presented classes of pesticides. So, in 2017, the share of detection of residual quantities of OCPs in products was 93%, by 2018 it increased by another 3%, in 2019 it decreased to 92% and in subsequent years there was a tendency to decrease (respectively, in 2020 80% and 2021 72%. The detection of residual levels of organophosphorus pesticides in food over a five-year observation period was of an intermittent nature and varied up to 2020 within 1-7%, but in 2021 there was a sharp jump of 20%. This may be due to the high demand for crop production due to its export growth.

The content of synthetic pesticides in food products practically did not go beyond the hygienic standards (SanPiN No. 0009-21)

Chemical analysis showed that organochlorine pesticides (OCPs) are represented by alpha-, beta- and gamma-hexachlorocyclohexane, dichlorodiphenyl, trichloromethylmethane, dichlorodiphenyldichloromethylmethane, dichlorodiphenyldichloroethylene, heptachlor, aldrin, hexachlorobenzene. Among organophosphorus pesticides, food products are contaminated with karbofos, chlorophos, phosphamide, Bi-58, and fosalone.

As you know, food products of animal origin are the main sources of OCP intake in the human body. OCPs are lipophilic and are often found in such a common product as milk. It was revealed that in most cases residual amounts of traces of dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane, hexachlorobenzene are detected in milk.

Characteristically, COP in the body accumulates in adipose tissues, in particular, the mammary glands of lactating women, and is very slowly excreted from the tissues [11]. OCPs have the ability to suppress the action of respiratory cycle enzymes and block the functional activity of the

thiol group of proteins [5]. They have a negative effect on the immune and hormonal systems, cause anemia, disrupt the activity of digestive enzymes, etc. [1, 6].

Fig1. Share of pesticide residues detected by laboratory method in foodstuffs by years in the republic

Continued Fig1. Share of pesticide residues detected by laboratory method in foodstuffs by years in the republic

It is known that the main sources of organophosphorus pesticides entering the human body are plant products contaminated with pesticides during the processing of crops. Chemical analysis in food products revealed such organophosphorus pesticides (OP) as phosphamide, karbofos, chlorophos, Bi-58, fozalon.

The most widespread use of phosphamide is noted. It is known that this pesticide is characterized by systemic action. Unlike karbaphos, it is able to quickly penetrate plants (including the edible part), which makes it effective in the fight against gnawing and sucking pests. It is used to control beet flea by ground spraying. Also, phosphamide, having a high initial toxicity, is able to destroy many insects and mites. Thus, protection of plants is provided in the most vulnerable phases of the initial period of growth. Moreover, the drug is highly stable in the external environment.

In general, lettuce, spinach, herbs, bell peppers, tomatoes, potatoes, carrots, cucumbers, eggplants, green beans, cauliflower, broccoli, peas, and grapes are affected to varying degrees by residual amounts of organophosphorus pesticides.

The mechanism of action of organophosphate pesticides is based on the inhibition and activity of acetylcholinesterase in the nervous system, leading to an increase in the level of acetylcholine, leading to increased excitation, muscle paralysis and blocking of the respiratory center, which is expressed in increased heart rate, development of convulsions and paralysis [9, 10].

It should be noted that the concentration of pesticides in food products may depend on the concentration of the drug, the form of its application, the multiplicity, processing time and the time elapsed from the last treatment to harvest. Currently, the choice of pesticides, control over the regulations and recommendations for the use of pesticides rests largely with the manufacturer and is often violated due to their professional illiteracy.

Conclusion

The analysis of the obtained data makes it possible to identify the sources and intensity of contamination with residual amounts of pesticides in food products. Persistent organic pollutants: organochlorine and organophosphorus pesticides are of particular danger from the point of view of the ongoing widespread contamination of crop and livestock products.

The problems of implementing sanitary and hygienic monitoring of contamination with residual amounts of pesticides are associated with the multicomponent composition of the determined pesticides, and the presence of a significant number of chemical matrices interfering with the release of the target pesticide, which leads to the search for optimal conditions for sample preparation.

Solving the problem of minimizing the negative impact of pesticide residues on public health is largely associated with compliance with hygienic regulations for the safe use of chemicals and improving methods of analytical control.

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1 МАХСУС СОН

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